

Digital Competitiveness

July 2025

The **Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport** is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The project POLICY ANSWERS monitors the implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda, and the broader context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this Monitoring Card, you find the results of the third round of data collection during 2024 and the first months of 2025 in comparison to the data collected in the previous second monitoring round.

In terms of Digital Competitiveness, the monitoring focuses on the context indicator “Individuals frequently using the internet” and various achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Note
Data not available for Albania (2017, 2024), Bosnia and Herzegovina (2017, 2022), Kosovo* (2021, 2024), North Macedonia (2023).

Source
Eurostat, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tin00092/default/table?lang=en> (accessed 13 February 2025).

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Regional Indicators

Western Balkans participation in the European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH) Network

Western Balkans Economy Indicators

Rapid transformative technological development for a competitive Western Balkans region A Europe fit for the digital age

| Indicator and overall assessment of the region | Development and linking of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH) |
|--|--|---|---|---|---|---|
| Albania | Increased number of DIHs and partnerships |
| Bosnia and Herzegovina | No new DIHs established
Increased number of partnerships |
| Kosovo | New EDIH launched
No information on partnerships provided |
| Montenegro | No new DIHs created
No information on partnerships provided |
| North Macedonia | Increased number of DIHs and partnerships |
| Serbia | Increased number of DIHs and partnerships |

Legend: Information not available

Highlights

All Western Balkans economies are associated to the Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL)
7 projects from Albania, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia are funded under the Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) and integrated in the Network of European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH)

